

Milestone: MS22 - Recommendations on data curation and ELSI compliance

Lead Participant: VIB

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Due: January 2024

Date Of Completion: 28 Feb 2024

Means of Verification

The mean of verification is the deliverable *D6.6 - Report outlining the recommendations on data curation and ELSI compliance.*

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes. The deliverable D6.6 was delayed and since it is the main mean of verification of this milestone, the milestone followed the delay.

Project participants & others

WP6 members, specially task 6.2 contributed to this milestone

Next action steps

Discussion around data curation procedures will continue during the project. Next discussions will involve how to help nodes decide if data quality should be used for filtering data.

